

ANONYMIZED Activity Form

1. Email *

Introductory Tasks

The process of these tasks are to explore the concept of refactoring and different forms of it.

Your primary task will be to investigate pull requests on GitHub. For all pull requests, only accept those that are refactoring: alterations to the code without changing the external behavior of the code.

Each of the tasks will contain a link to a pull request to which you can respond with your questions.

Task 1

Task link here: [x]

2. Is this code change a refactoring (i.e. it does not change the external behavior)?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, it is a refactoring.
- No, it changes the code's behavior.
- I don't know.

3. What impact does this code change have?

If it is a refactoring, does the refactoring improve the legibility, maintainability, or something else? If it is not a refactoring, what behavior does this pull request change? If you do not know, what feature of the code are you unsure about?

4. What tools or strategies did you use to investigate the differences in the code?

Explain in a comment what strategies you used in comparison. Did you use an IDE? Did you use the unified or split view in GitHub? Did you run the test suite? All of the above? None of the above?

5. Was there anything difficult about comparing this code?

Task 2

Task link here: [x]

6. Is this code change a refactoring (i.e. it does not change the external behavior)?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, it is a refactoring.
- No, it changes the code's behavior.
- I don't know.

7. What impact does this code change have?

If it is a refactoring, does the refactoring improve the legibility, maintainability, or something else? If it is not a refactoring, what behavior does this pull request change? If you do not know, what feature of the code are you unsure about?

8. What tools or strategies did you use to investigate the differences in the code?

Explain in a comment what strategies you used in comparison. Did you use an IDE? Did you use the unified or split view in GitHub? Did you run the test suite? All of the above? None of the above?

9. Was there anything difficult about comparing this code?

Task 3

Task link here: [x]

10. Is this code change a refactoring (i.e. it does not change the external behavior)?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, it is a refactoring.
- No, it changes the code's behavior.
- I don't know.

11. What impact does this code change have?

If it is a refactoring, does the refactoring improve the legibility, maintainability, or something else? If it is not a refactoring, what behavior does this pull request change? If you do not know, what feature of the code are you unsure about?

12. What tools or strategies did you use to investigate the differences in the code?

Explain in a comment what strategies you used in comparison. Did you use an IDE? Did you use the unified or split view in GitHub? Did you run the test suite? All of the above? None of the above?

13. Was there anything difficult about comparing this code?

Task 4

Task link here: [x]

14. Is this code change a refactoring (i.e. it does not change the external behavior)?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, it is a refactoring.
- No, it changes the code's behavior.
- I don't know.

15. What impact does this code change have?

If it is a refactoring, does the refactoring improve the legibility, maintainability, or something else? If it is not a refactoring, what behavior does this pull request change? If you do not know, what feature of the code are you unsure about?

16. What tools or strategies did you use to investigate the differences in the code?

Explain in a comment what strategies you used in comparison. Did you use an IDE? Did you use the unified or split view in GitHub? Did you run the test suite? All of the above? None of the above?

17. Was there anything difficult about comparing this code?

Task 5

Task link here: [x]

18. Is this code change a refactoring (i.e. it does not change the external behavior)?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, it is a refactoring.
- No, it changes the code's behavior.
- I don't know.

19. What impact does this code change have?

If it is a refactoring, does the refactoring improve the legibility, maintainability, or something else? If it is not a refactoring, what behavior does this pull request change? If you do not know, what feature of the code are you unsure about?

20. What tools or strategies did you use to investigate the differences in the code?

Explain in a comment what strategies you used in comparison. Did you use an IDE? Did you use the unified or split view in GitHub? Did you run the test suite? All of the above? None of the above?

21. Was there anything difficult about comparing this code?

Task 6

Task link here: [x]

22. Is this code change a refactoring (i.e. it does not change the external behavior)?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, it is a refactoring.
- No, it changes the code's behavior.
- I don't know.

23. What impact does this code change have?

If it is a refactoring, does the refactoring improve the legibility, maintainability, or something else? If it is not a refactoring, what behavior does this pull request change? If you do not know, what feature of the code are you unsure about?

24. What tools or strategies did you use to investigate the differences in the code?

Explain in a comment what strategies you used in comparison. Did you use an IDE? Did you use the unified or split view in GitHub? Did you run the test suite? All of the above? None of the above?

25. Was there anything difficult about comparing this code?

Task 7

Task link here: [x]

26. Is this code change a refactoring (i.e. it does not change the external behavior)?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, it is a refactoring.
- No, it changes the code's behavior.
- I don't know.

27. What impact does this code change have?

If it is a refactoring, does the refactoring improve the legibility, maintainability, or something else? If it is not a refactoring, what behavior does this pull request change? If you do not know, what feature of the code are you unsure about?

28. What tools or strategies did you use to investigate the differences in the code?

Explain in a comment what strategies you used in comparison. Did you use an IDE? Did you use the unified or split view in GitHub? Did you run the test suite? All of the above? None of the above?

29. Was there anything difficult about comparing this code?

Task 8

Task link here: [x]

30. Is this code change a refactoring (i.e. it does not change the external behavior)?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, it is a refactoring.
- No, it changes the code's behavior.
- I don't know.

31. What impact does this code change have?

If it is a refactoring, does the refactoring improve the legibility, maintainability, or something else? If it is not a refactoring, what behavior does this pull request change? If you do not know, what feature of the code are you unsure about?

32. What tools or strategies did you use to investigate the differences in the code?

Explain in a comment what strategies you used in comparison. Did you use an IDE? Did you use the unified or split view in GitHub? Did you run the test suite? All of the above? None of the above?

33. Was there anything difficult about comparing this code?

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